

Interview with Music Composer Tarō Iwashiro

Andrés Domenech Alcaide

CoolJapan.es

In July 2018, CoolJapan.es had the opportunity to meet Tarō Iwashiro during the third edition of the MOSMA festival, a music event specialised in film scores and soundtracks related to sequential art—specially cinema, but also animation and video games. That year brought together renowned artists from around the world, including John Powell, Jeff Beal, Víctor Reyes, and Tarō Iwashiro himself, all of whom have received numerous awards for their contributions to the world of music.

Iwashiro not only participated in a magnificent concert—composing new pieces specifically for the occasion and conducting his own music—but also held a meeting with fans, where he spoke with attendees at the Cervantes Theatre in Málaga about his work and career. He also took part in a signing session that he seemed reluctant to end, moved by the warmth and appreciation he received in a country as distant to him as Spain.

The orchestra and choir of the Cabildo Catedral de Córdoba also took part in MOSMA 2018 alongside Iwashiro, who visited the Mosque–Cathedral of Córdoba as part of the event. A concert featuring his music was also held in this emblematic monument.

Musical talent was already present in Tarō Iwashiro’s family through his father, Kōichi Iwashiro, a composer who, among other works, arranged and compiled traditional Russian and Japanese songs, and who became a fundamental influence in Tarō’s life. Born in Tokyo in 1965, Tarō Iwashiro graduated from the Tokyo National University of Fine Arts and Music in 1984. He later studied composition at Tokyo University of the Arts, graduating with top honours and obtaining his master’s degree there in 1991.

Shortly thereafter, in 1992, he began working as a composer in the film industry with *Kachō Shima Kōsaku*, based on the manga by Kenshi Hirokane. Over the years, he has become a specialist in soundtrack composition, although he has also composed independent music outside audiovisual works. He has worked on both animated productions—such as *The Heroic Legend of Arslan* (2015) and *Rurouni Kenshin: The Motion Picture* (1997), based on the manga by Nobuhiro Watsuki—as well as live-action films and series, including *Memories of Murder* (2003) and even video games such as *Onimusha 2: Samurai's Destiny* (2002) and *Blade & Soul* (2012).

Particularly noteworthy is his collaboration with Chinese-born director John Woo, who has worked with Iwashiro since their collaboration on *Red Cliff* (2008), for which he composed a highly acclaimed score. Iwashiro's style draws heavily from classical music, placing great emphasis on orchestral work, while also incorporating electronic music and synthesisers. His compositions often feature a distinctive blend of Western and Asian musical elements, adapted to the needs of each project.

Tarō Iwashiro is not only a composer but also an accomplished conductor of his own works, frequently collaborating closely with orchestras. He has worked with symphonic and philharmonic orchestras around the world, including those in Tokyo, Paris, and Moscow. He has received numerous awards throughout his career, and his music has gained increasing recognition in the West, particularly following his work on films such as *Memories of Murder* by Bong Joon-ho and *Red Cliff* by John Woo, for which he received an award from the Chinese Academy.

During MOSMA 2018, his work as a composer was honoured with the Goldspirit Award “Music From The Soul,” specifically recognising his role in the album *Spiritual Songs*, a project that brought together prominent Japanese musicians to support victims of the devastating tsunami that struck Japan in 2011.

Tarō Iwashiro at the centre, accompanied by Isabel Vázquez and musician Kayoko Morimoto—who, once again, served as our interpreter—during the meeting with fans and the press at the Cervantes Theatre in Málaga.

Interview with Tarō Iwashiro

Cool Japan: How long have you been interested in working as a composer? What does music mean to you? Did you intend from the beginning to build your professional career around music?

Tarō Iwashiro: I began to feel a love for music at around ten years old, at least if I rely on my own memory. However, my parents have often said that even when I was four or five years old, I reacted very strongly to music, and they were certain that I liked it. I have a younger sister—three years younger than me, to be exact. Despite having the same parents, she did not show the same response to music that they saw in me. As an adult, she did not pursue a career in music, but instead became a designer.

I just remembered something that is not directly related to your question, but I think it may help answer it. About five years ago, when Juan Ramón [Iwashiro is referring to Juan Ramón Hernández, a member of the BSOSpirit team and one of the organizers of MOSMA] contacted me, I discovered that I had many followers in Spain—that there are many enthusiasts of film music here, and of my work in particular. I couldn't believe it! At first, I thought it must be a joke, or that someone would eventually ask me for money for some music or project. But as I spoke more with him and his team, I realized everything was genuine, although I remained quite surprised.

This morning [referring to the meeting with fans at the Cervantes Theatre], they mentioned *Marco* (*Haha wo tazunete sanzenri*, the 1999 version for which I composed the music), and you can believe me when I say I was truly impressed by how popular that character was in your country and across Europe... I still find it hard to believe that so many people know my music and genuinely enjoy it. I am finally beginning to process it, although it is still difficult.

When I saw the fans so enthusiastic about the piece I had just premiered during the gala, and even Juan Ramón in tears [to whom Iwashiro dedicated his new composition, *Dear J*], I became fully convinced that everything happening to me was real. If next year I were to write a second piece dedicated to Juan Ramón, I think he wouldn't cry anymore—he'd be fed up with it! [laughs]

Going back to your questions, I have loved music for over forty years, but I had never experienced anything like this—coming to a place whose language I do not speak, yet finding so many people moved by my music. This reinforces my belief that music does not require any language other than itself to be understood. It connects people without the need for words—in other words, music is a universal language. I feel a great sense of happiness experiencing this here, in this place, meeting so many people who, from afar, know my work.

I am also beginning to experience another feeling within myself, since today's rehearsals [referring to the MOSMA 2018 concert, where Iwashiro served as guest conductor of his own music].

I have previously worked in London, Paris, Moscow, and Los Angeles with orchestras in those cities, so I already have experience working with orchestras outside Japan... but I had never witnessed what I have experienced here in Spain. After the rehearsal, the musicians themselves came up to me to say that they love my music, that they admire my work, and that they would give their very best to deliver a great performance in the concert the following day—one worthy of my compositions. Moreover, the members of the Cabildo Catedral de Córdoba orchestra even refused to take a break when I offered it...

They wanted to keep playing my music!

Because of this, I now feel that everything I had experienced was not a mistake, and that tomorrow's concert will be a wonderful experience—a great performance. I am completely certain that the day and the concert will leave me with an unforgettable memory to take back to Tokyo.

When I am conducting, there are moments when I feel a true connection—a sense of *feeling*—between the performers and myself as conductor. Those moments are what make me happiest as a musician.

Tarō Iwashiro while answering a fan who asked him about the *Marco* series. At first, he appeared thoughtful and pleasantly surprised that someone in our country remembered the series with such affection, and spoke about his music for the 1999 version with such respect.

CJ: Do you enjoy film music not only as a composer, but also as an enthusiast who listens to it? Which of your works have been your favourites?

TI: Of course—I love not only cinema, but also film music. I not only watch many films in my free time, but I also listen to many film soundtracks. I have a large DVD film collection.

As for musical genres... well, my tastes are not oriented toward specific genres, nor do I have a particular favourite. However, I can tell you what kind of works I enjoy the most, or those in which I feel the greatest satisfaction.

My favourite kind of work is the one that manages to communicate one hundred percent of what I want to express as a composer, what the director of a work is aiming for, and in which I can communicate with the director on a human level—whether in anime, film, or television series. I am indifferent toward any specific work I have composed, beyond trying to experience this feeling in all of them. I need to feel that I am able to convey the director's vision exactly as they imagined it for the scenes—to translate their ideas into music. That is the kind of work I enjoy the most.

However, when people such as producers, sponsors, or distributors begin to interfere in these conversations and interactions between the director and myself, I stop enjoying the work. Even so, I continue working with a smile, maintaining a positive attitude and trying to preserve good relationships... but reluctantly, as it is not a way of working that appeals to me.

CJ: What can you tell us about your training and education, Mr. Iwashiro? Which musical artists have influenced you the most in your work, both Japanese and Western?

TI: Of course, the first influence on my work has been my father, Kōichi. Since I entered university, there have been several composers whose work I have listened to extensively, to whom I have devoted many hours of study, and who have deeply interested me—such as Ludwig van Beethoven, Richard Wagner, Béla Bartók, and Claude Debussy. All of them are closely associated with classical music.

Beyond classical music, there are also artists who have influenced me, including many from the American continent, such as jazz musicians like guitarist Pat Metheny and Keith Jarrett, as well as musician and producer David Foster. I am also very fond of Claus Ogermann's work, particularly his jazz arrangements, and the music of Peter Gabriel. During my university years, I listened to them almost obsessively.

As for synthesiser music, I am passionate about the work of Jean-Michel Jarre, a true pioneer in this field. And when it comes to film music, I believe that for me—and for everyone—the great references are Ennio Morricone and John Williams. Therefore, many artists from very diverse musical genres have influenced my work and career.

Speaking of Japanese composers, there are two in particular whom I greatly admire, and unfortunately both have already passed away. One of them is Isao Tomita, who also worked with electronic music, and the other is Tōru Takemitsu, who worked with both traditional Japanese music and Western classical music, separately and in combination.

CJ: You are a composer with an extensive professional career, having worked with people from all over the world, such as John Woo and Bong Joon-ho. What can you tell us about the experience of working with international teams, including those in Hollywood?

TI: I think the best way to explain it would be to talk about my experience with John Woo. I have been working with him for more than ten years now, composing for all his projects during that time. Over the years, his team has changed, and I am the only one who has consistently remained. I often wonder what the reason for that might be, and honestly... I have no idea! [laughs]

In Spain, you have the saying “familiarity breeds contempt,” and in Japan we have a similar way of understanding this idea [laughs]. Let me explain.

When I work with someone for a long time, I get to know them better and gradually build trust, reaching a point where I understand them very well. However, sometimes I feel that we cross a line when I notice a harsher or less respectful attitude from a director as a result of that familiarity, and I tend to think that I may have done something wrong. That is why I am always cautious about becoming too familiar with someone, because I find it difficult to understand when I may have upset them or done something incorrectly. I may even begin to think that something in my work is truly wrong if I am spoken to in an aggressive or impolite tone.

Tarō Iwashiro alongside Kayoko Morimoto during the composer’s meeting with fans at the Cervantes Theatre in Málaga

TI: This has never happened to me with John Woo. He is a very gentle, respectful, and kind person, who invites you to trust him from the very beginning. Over the years I have worked with him, I have developed a great deal of trust, yet he is someone who never forgets to maintain proper manners with his team, who is grateful for the work of others, and who never crosses certain boundaries or loses his composure. This is precisely what makes me trust him even more and feel more comfortable working on his projects, always feeling grateful for the opportunity to collaborate with him.

I believe I have a duty, no matter what happens, to maintain composure and respect towards others, thanks to the upbringing I received from my father. It is something I always saw in him. It is also an attitude I have observed in John Woo. That is why, at times, I feel that John is like a second father to me. As he is much older than I am, it would be natural to think that he will pass away before me... and I believe that the day he does, I will feel as though I have lost a father.

I think that understanding professional relationships in the way my father did—or as John Woo does—is one of the reasons why he enjoys working with me, and why he continues to trust me and my compositions as part of his filmography. As a human being, I believe he is truly exceptional. Simply put, a good person.

CJ: When working on a director's project as a composer, what is your level of involvement? For example, do you first watch the scenes you need to compose for, or has it ever been the case that a scene is adapted to your work?

TI: I never interfere in script decisions, and I try not to contribute ideas to the writers or the director. I want to respect their vision one hundred per cent. Once I am contacted to join a project, I have two ways of working. The first begins with reading the script. At that moment, I already start forming ideas in my mind about the music that could accompany it. I even compose a test piece—a kind of sketch—and present these samples when filming begins. In this case, I do not compose something fully defined or complete, nor do I take into account the specific setting being filmed. Instead, I work with a musical “image” of the project, thinking about what kind of music would suit the work as a whole.

That is where I pause. At that point, I encounter two types of directors. The first respond as soon as they receive my samples, expressing whether or not they agree with the music I have created. They comment on possible changes in sound, style, or character, helping to define the direction. I usually maintain dialogue with them from the very beginning. Others, however, do not respond until filming has concluded.

I usually attend the filming in person for the projects I work on. I do so because I believe I must be in the same place as the director, actors, and crew in order to feel, see, and understand the director's vision, and how my work will fit within it. This later makes my job easier, whether I need to compose additional music or make changes at the director's request, as it helps me better understand their vision of the work.

After filming comes the editing process, which is the second way in which I work on a project. It is at this stage that we finally adapt the music precisely to each scene and moment where it is intended to appear. This is also when I compose more music. I constantly take into account the editing process, during which scenes may be altered, removed, or modified... adjusting my music accordingly depending on the moment and the director's need to emphasise certain characters or actions.

There are also cases where the director was unable to film certain scenes as intended, or decides to shoot new ones. In many such situations, directors ask me to help accompany these new scenes with music, or to adapt my compositions to the various cuts made during editing. They may also ask me, when scenes are added or removed, to readapt music I originally composed for other sequences, or to modify it to avoid abrupt cuts and ensure smooth transitions, so that the soundtrack contributes to the coherence of the film's structure.

Naturally, it also happens that my music does not convince the director for certain sequences, leading to the removal of specific musical segments for scenes they feel work better without a score. The opposite can also occur, where I am asked to compose music for scenes in which it is considered essential—for example, to associate it with a particular setting.

During the editing stage, we also take marketing into account. In other words, we must consider the target audience for the film or series—whether it is intended for children, adults, or all audiences. For this reason, at this stage I must keep in mind that I need to compose my music with specific audience groups in mind.

Tarō Iwashiro at the centre, being interviewed by our colleague Andrés Domenech Alcaide, with Kayoko Morimoto acting as interpreter, at the Hotel Palacio Málaga, where he granted us this interview.

CJ: To conclude... could you tell us what you are currently working on, and what differences you have found when composing for video games?

TI: In that regard, I am currently composing for a Japanese film, and I will begin recording its music in November this year [referring to 2018]. I still have a few months, but I have already started working on the final aspects I mentioned earlier. In fact, I began this project just before travelling to Spain.

In addition, I am working on a literary project of my own that I would like to adapt into a film, and about which I will speak soon. And of course, you will soon find new compositions by me in future works by John Woo.

As for video games, the first thing to bear in mind is that the development process is very long. At first, I wondered whether you were asking about the music or about the whole production, but in reality, my work on a video game begins almost at the very start of development. I usually compose for large-scale productions, which makes the time I spend working on video games even longer.

You enjoy video games, although I am not a player myself. Even so, I find them interesting, and the way I work on them is quite curious. For instance, I sometimes receive requests to compose music for a specific level or setting. I then create a piece or theme as a kind of “demo”.

The developers programme the music into the game to see how it works when playing through a level, but I am usually not present, nor do I interfere in how the team chooses to integrate my music into the environment. They test the level with my music, and this is when feedback begins. They contact me and ask for something different if they feel what I composed does not fit their vision for the level, or they request changes to adapt my work to it.

Sometimes this feedback process is repeated many times, and I find myself in communication with development teams for up to two years. At that point, I start to wonder... “Is this game ever going to be released?” [laughs].

Since I am not a gamer myself, I cannot help but be surprised by how important music is in video games, and by how complex and lengthy the development process is. I do not fully understand it, as it is something new to me, but I try to grasp it nonetheless.

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Finally, we extend our thanks and congratulations to Tarō Iwashiro himself, of whom we can only say that he has shown the CoolJapan.es team that he is not only a highly talented and skilled professional, but also a very humble person, who consistently demonstrates remarkable warmth, attentiveness, and dedication towards his audience.

Following this link, the message Iwashiro dedicated to the CoolJapan.es team and readers.

Sources

- **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] |
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